

CLARIN-CH Training Sessions 2025: Exploring Swiss Language Resources and Tools

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This training series took place in 2025 and was organized by members of the CLARIN-CH ecosystem of infrastructures with the aim to introduce and deepen participants' knowledge of the Swiss national infrastructure for language data. The development of the sessions was supported by the projects *Upgrading the linguistic ORD-ecosystem* (UpLORD) and *Moving towards a national FAIR-compliant ecosystem of Federated Infrastructure for Language Data* (FAIR-FI-LD), co-funded through the swissuniversities' Open Science I program. The online training series was a collaborative effort of:

- CLARIN-CH Coordination Office: Cristina Grisot, CLARIN-CH National Coordinator
- UZH Linguistic Research Infrastructure LiRI: Teodora Vuković, post-doc, Jeremy Zehr, application engineer, and Maaïke Kellenberger Communication Strategist
- ZHAW Digital Discourse Lab: Julia Krasselt, professor at Digital Discourse Lab
- Language Repository of Switzerland LaRS@SWISSUbase: Christian Futter, Data Expert, and Stefanie Strebel, Data Team Lead (UZH Library)
- Università della Svizzera italiana: Johanna Miecznikowski-Fuenfschilling, professor at Institute of Italian Studies and the Institute of argumentation, linguistics and semiotics

Covering topics such as corpus querying, media data collection, multimodal data modeling, and data sharing, these sessions provided hands-on insights into key tools and methodologies that could be useful for researchers working with language data. The training sessions were designed following the FAIR-by-design methodology for Open Educational Resources developed by the skills4EOSC project, which was adapted to organizers' educational needs.

The sessions were held every second Monday during the 2025 spring semester, online on Zoom, from 15:30 to 17:00, and were recorded.

- **Introduction to the CLARIN-CH ecosystem of infrastructures in the era of Open Research Data** (10 March 2025, Cristina Grisot); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826373>
- **LiRI Corpus Platform: Data Model and Query** (17 March 2025, Teodora Vuković and Jeremy Zehr); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826465>
- **Querying and analysing Swiss media data with Swissdix@LiRI** (31 March 2025, Maaïke Kellenberger); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826432>
- **LiRI Corpus Platform: Data Analysis Using Text, Audio, and Video Corpora** (14 April 2025, Teodora Vuković); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826505>
- **Modelling of Multi-Modal Data in LiRI Corpus Platform and Beyond** (28 April 2025, Johanna Miecznikowski-Fuenfschilling, Jeremy Zehr); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826562>
- **Data analysis with Swiss-AL for textual data** (12 May 2025, Julia Krasselt); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826591>

- **Publishing Data on the Language Repository of Switzerland (LaRS)** (26 May 2025, Christian Futter and Stefanie Strebel); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826402>
- **Reusing data for teaching and secondary analyses** (2 June 2025, Julia Krasselt); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826623>

More information:

Filiposka, S. (2023, Dezember 4). FAIR-by-Design Methodology:How to Develop FAIR Materials. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10256852>

Filiposka, S., Mishev, A., Anastasopoulou, A., Frontini, F., Pedonese, G., & van der Lek, I. (2024, September 20). FAIR-by-Design training for the CLARIN community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13816183>

Filiposka, S., Green, D., Mishev, A., Kjorveziroski, V., Corleto, A., Napolitano, E., Paolini, G., Di Giorgio, S., Janik, J., Schirru, L., Gingold, A., Hadrossek, C., Souyiultzoglou, I., Leister, C., Pavone, G., Sharma, S., Mendez Rodriguez, E. M., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305540>